

Use case fact-sheet

Actors

List all actors involved in the Use Case and the Geographic Information-related processes they are involved in, then put a “x” in correspondence to the relevant cells.

Who (actor) ²	What (Action) ¹					
	Data acquisition/creation	Data analysis/processing/validation	Data publication	Extraction of information from published data	Data maintenance	xxx
Municipality	x		x			
Data providers	x	x				
Decision makers					x	
Officers/technicians			x	x	x	
Researchers		x			x	
General Public					x	

Table 1: Overview of the actors involved in the Use Case

Use Case (UC) main info	
Identifier	GR_3-30-300
Name	Building classification with 3-30-300 criteria
Description	The use case classifies residential buildings according to 3 criteria: 1. the number of visible trees, 2. the percentage of tree canopy coverage within the district and 3. the distance to green or blue infrastructures
Primary User	Urban planners
Goal	To estimate the current nature access in the city, to identify areas where buildings have limited access to nature and to plan changes
Owner	DEDA (to be discussed)
Status	Tool metadata finalised Data metadata finalised Data collection ongoing Tools implementation ongoing
Policy context	

¹ Add new processes or rename the existing ones or split the ones currently merged as you may find more appropriate

² Add new actors or rename the existing ones

<p>Challenges & Priorities</p>	<p><i>The climate conditions in Graz are influenced by its geographical position and the constant climate change at the global level. Some of the main climate challenges of Graz are related to the increase in the average annual temperatures, which are especially felt in densely built areas. Graz is also prone to severe flooding from short, intense rainfalls, which overwhelm the city's sewer systems and streams. Moreover, the geographical setting of Graz contributes to poor air quality. Its topographical location in a basin surrounded by hills, with limited airflow, results in stagnant air and elevated levels of pollutants from traffic and heating sources.</i></p> <p><i>These climate risks have been acknowledged by the city administration, which devised several policy strategies and cross-sectoral action plans.</i></p>
<p>Strategy/Plan/Regulation</p>	<p><i>The Climate Adaptation Action Plan describes plausible climate change effects for the people, infrastructure, and nature in Graz and provides measures for 11 pressing topics (Stadt Graz – Umweltamt, 2018), including urban green spaces. In order to tackle problems in these fields in an optimal way, the climate adaptation action plan suggests priorities according to which the city should implement the measures. In the 2018 version of the plan, the focus is on greening measures for streets, places, and buildings, hoping that they will improve the urban climate primarily and additionally have positive effects on the biodiversity, noise protection, cooling of buildings, air quality, etc. – but also on social integration.</i></p> <p><i>In 2022 the city of Graz launched its Climate Protection Plan, which is the city's overarching strategy for achieving the climate protection goals. The preparation of this plan is considered as a continuous process, which is divided into three main parts:</i></p> <p><i>Part 1 deals with preparing the opening balance sheet, which shows the baseline situation of CO2 emissions in Graz and the required climate change objectives.</i></p>
<p>Local Green Deal / City contract(s)</p>	<p><i>Urban development concept 4.0 STEK (2013). The 4.0 STEK is an essential tool for the urban planning office, as it sets goals on how the city should develop within the next 15 years. Additionally, there are (prioritized) measures to reach those goals, which act as guidelines for all administrative departments.</i></p> <p><i>In March and April 2021 residents of Graz could submit ideas for a more livable Graz, which could be implemented with the funds from the so-called citizen's budget. Among the most popular ideas were several climate-related projects, also taking into account the presence of green in the urban area and its accessibility. Among them:</i></p> <p><i>SAVE THE BEES (€100,000): Planting of flower meadows on urban green spaces and establishment of three apiary areas in cooperation with beekeepers;</i></p>

	<p><i>WILDFLOWER MEADOWS FOR GRAZ (€100,000): Planting of about 10,000 m2 wildflower meadows in urban green spaces;</i></p> <p><i>MARGARETENBAD FRONT GARDEN ((€100,000): Redesigning and greening the front garden of the Margaretenbad, including replacing the concrete by green areas ;</i></p> <p><i>TREES IN THE CITY CENTER ((€100,000): Planting of extra trees in the area of Harrachgasse (Geidorf district)</i></p> <p><i>CITY'S FOREST AREAS (€50,000): Preservation and extension of the forest areas in the city.</i></p>
<p>European Green Deal Policy Area</p>	<p>This use case contributes to two EU Green Deal policy areas, both the EU's climate ambition for 2030 and 2050; and preserving and restoring ecosystems. More specifically, the first policy area is related EUs' priorities related to climate adaptation. The EU Strategy for Adaptation sets the framework for achieving a climate-neutral and fully adapted society by 2050 by promoting among other actions, nature-based solutions. In the perimeter of the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030, this use case can provide support for the realisation of afforestation and reforestation target and greening of urban and peri-urban areas.</p> <p>The implementation of these actions aims to respond to the needs of adaptation to climate change at the local level and provide support to local authorities engaged in systematically incorporating and promoting green infrastructures and nature-based solutions in urban planning.</p>
<p>Precondition</p>	
<p><i>Sharing of Graz data within USAGE - agreed!</i></p>	
<p>Postcondition</p>	
<p>DRI (Decision Ready Information)</p>	<p>Graz hexagon result 3-30-300 classification https://usage.geocat.live/catalogue/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/c9c64337-8bae-484b-a959-cda5557b7c39</p>
<p>Use of DRI</p>	<p><i>By monitoring nature access for each residential building, decision makers can guide strategic investments in urban greening.</i></p>
<p>Use case processing steps</p>	
<p><i>Insert the link to the BPMN representation of the use case</i> https://app.diagrams.net/#G1qFrLmP-Gye-clbWZaUtHoiv6r1tKPY3e#%7B%22pageId%22%3A%22Krvi3zqOJTbH_F1lKnKt%22%7D</p>	
<p>DOI to processing steps BPMN</p>	
<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15168023</p>	

